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Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

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D3.4 – Report about the societal acceptance and recommendations for improvement

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List of abbreviations	
AESN	l'Agence de l'Eau Seine-Normandie
BCE	Before Common Era
BREEAM	Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method
CAAE	Comité Andaluz de Agricultura Ecológica
CE	Common Era
CE	Conformité Européenne
CMC	Component Material Category
CPH	Centre de production horticole
DEVE	Direction des Espaces verts et de l'Environnement
EEA	European Economic Area
ENPC	École nationale des ponts et chaussées
ESS	European Social Survey
EU	European Union
FPR	Fertilising Products Regulation
HEDF	human excreta-derived fertilisers
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
NIMBY	not in my backyard
P&MA	Paris Métropole Aménagement
PFC	Product Function Category
QR (Code)	Quick Response (Code)
STEA	Service Technique Eau et Assainissement
SVDP	Saint-Vincent-de-Paul
WP	Work Package
WTP	willingness to pay

Executive summary

This deliverable examines the social acceptance of human excreta-derived fertilisers (HEDF) within the P2GreenN project and formulates recommendations and tools to support their wider uptake. Recycling nutrients from locally available human excreta is essential to closing nutrient loops and implementing the EU Farm to Fork strategy. Still, HEDF face strong socio-cultural stigma, risk perceptions and regulatory ambiguity. Drawing on theories of technology acceptance, NIMBY, risk perception, trust, and willingness to pay, the research behind this report examines how and why public acceptance of HEDF varies across localities, shaped by perceived benefits and risks, institutional trust, and broader environmental attitudes. The analysis covers three pilot regions (Axarquía in Spain, Gotland in Sweden, North German Plain in Germany) and four follower regions (Italy, Greece, Hungary, Paris/France), partly contextualised by Eurobarometer and ESS data on environmental concern and sustainable consumption.

Empirically, the report combines four strands of evidence: (i) an online survey of everyday people in six countries (Spain, Sweden, Germany, Greece, Italy, Hungary) to assess trust, NIMBY attitudes, perceived risks and willingness to pay; (ii) focus group discussions with stakeholders in all seven regions (farmers, technology providers, utilities, food processors, experts, local authorities); (iii) semi-structured interviews with additional stakeholders; and (iv) an internal survey of P2GreenN consortium members on the effectiveness of field visits.

Across cases, farmers are pragmatically open to using HEDF if products are agronomically reliable, licensed, and cost-competitive. In contrast, consumers are more hesitant, especially when fertilisation practices are made explicit on labels or associated with terms such as “human excreta” or “wastewater”. Trust is generally higher in private companies than in public authorities, especially in Hungary, where confidence in governments is particularly low. NIMBY responses are widespread: respondents are more willing to accept HEDF in nearby green areas than to host processing facilities, with acceptance highest in Sweden and Germany and lowest in Greece and Hungary. Concerns focus mainly on odour, followed by environmental contamination and infection risk, and willingness to pay for HEDF-fertilised products declines from North to South and East, aligning with EU-wide patterns of pro-environmental behaviour.

The qualitative material highlights that acceptance is strongly context-dependent. In Spain and Greece, water scarcity and water quality debates are central, while in Germany and Sweden, high generalised trust and familiarity with manure or urine use support comparatively favourable attitudes, even if pharmaceutical or hormone residues remain salient concerns. Italy and Hungary show pronounced conservatism, strong NIMBY dynamics and low willingness to retrofit sanitation infrastructure, but also identify environmentally conscious niches and the potential of co-planning and clear

communication. The Paris case, focused on new housing with source-separating toilets and internal municipal fertiliser use, demonstrates that structured awareness-raising (workshops, videos, field trials) and financial support can generate high, even enthusiastic acceptance among future residents. Across regions, stakeholders converge that acceptance depends on reframing wastewater as a resource, drawing analogies to familiar practices (livestock manure, free-range or “eco-friendly” products), and tailoring communication through trusted actors: local governments and municipalities, utilities, selected companies, experts and—more unevenly—NGOs, using social media, local newspapers and face-to-face events.

On this basis, the deliverable proposes a toolbox of tested instruments to enhance social acceptance. Physical field visits to pilot sites, supported by feedback surveys, are shown to help dispel doubts—especially about odour, noise and hygiene—while also revealing how geography and process specifics shape perceptions; 360° online “virtual field visits” can complement these where in-person visits are not feasible. A video game (“P2Green: Turning Waste into Green Wealth” – Deliverable 3.5) uses gamification to teach the circular economy and the nutrient cycle, targeting teenagers, young adults and educators and aiming to reduce psychological distance to HEDF. Co-designed logos, based on region-specific selling points (local resource use, surface-water protection, short value chains, circularity), offer a visual communication tool that can later be aligned with third-party certification. Finally, the report underlines both the potential and the regulatory challenges of certification: while stakeholders widely see trusted, third-party schemes as crucial for acceptance, current EU fertiliser and organic regulations do not yet provide clear pathways for urine- and faeces-based products, implying that in the short term P2Green must rely on national authorisations and that medium-term policy change will be needed to unlock whole market and social uptake.

1 Aim of the Social Acceptance investigation - Contextualisation

Recycling nutrients is a fundamental prerequisite for closing nutrient loops and effectively implementing the EU Farm to Fork strategy. The utilisation of locally available human excreta as a sustainable and cost-effective nutrient source offers a promising pathway to producing bio-based fertilisers that can substitute for mineral fertilisers. In turn, this can foster more environmentally friendly food production (Häfner et al., 2023; Krause et al., 2021) and contribute to circular solutions. Nevertheless, human excreta are predominantly perceived as an undesirable waste stream that generates environmental problems (Senecal & Vinnerås, 2017), thereby hindering efforts to “close the loop” from fork back to farm. The barriers to implementation are multifaceted, spanning technological challenges (Aliahmad et al., 2023) and regulatory ambiguities (see details in Deliverable 3.7, Scoping review in the legislative framework), even in countries often regarded as progressive in this domain, such as Sweden (McConville et al., 2017). Empirical analyses of social acceptance remain scarce, and existing findings show substantial cross-national variation (Lienert & Tove A., 2009).

To provide a more nuanced understanding and to support the broader deployment of human excreta-derived fertilisers (HEDF), thereby facilitating the green transition and the closure of nutrient loops in a wider spatial context, we examined the social acceptance of HEDF in three European pilot regions (Axarquía in Spain, Gotland in Sweden, North German Plain in Germany) and three follower regions (Hungary, Greece, Italy), and the notably successful Paris region (Figure 1). To uncover spatial differences and patterns in acceptance, we addressed the following research question: How and why does public acceptance of HEDF vary across localities, shaped by perceived benefits, perceived risks, and local contextual factors?

Figure 1: The P2Green regions

1.1 A hint of historical perspective

The utilisation of human excreta as fertiliser is not a recent innovation. The collection of night soil—used as a euphemism for human excrement—has historically been practised to varying degrees in urbanised contexts. Such collection and use have been particularly prominent in parts of Asia compared to the Western world (Szczygiel, 2020). Municipal sewerage systems were already present in ancient and medieval times, for instance in the Mesopotamian empires of Assyria and Babylonia (around 2500 BCE), as well as in the Indus civilisation at Mohenjo-daro (around 2550 BCE) (Gray, 1940). The use of human excreta as fertiliser has been a defining feature of traditional Chinese agriculture since the Song Dynasty (1127–1279 CE). It contributed to urban cleanliness and hygiene and was regarded as a “top-class fertiliser” during the Ming and Qing eras (1368–1912 CE) (Du et al., 2018). In Japan, the agricultural use of human waste dates back to the 12th century and night soil gained increasing importance over time (Szczygiel, 2020).

From the mid-19th century onwards, the widespread adoption of the flush toilet led to higher volumes of water entering urban faecal collection systems, substantially diluting night soil and diminishing its fertiliser value (Gandy, 2004; Kawa et al., 2019). The transition to hydraulic sanitation systems was closely intertwined with evolving notions

of hygiene and cleanliness, transforming urban social life and modes of governance, and giving rise to debates and contestations that persist globally (Kawa et al., 2019).

Since the 1970s, the value of human waste as a fertiliser has markedly declined, primarily due to the increased use of chemical fertilisers and rapid population growth, which together have contributed to serious waste management challenges in several regions of the world (Wang, 2024). At the same time, sewage sludge from urban wastewater treatment plants, which contains organic matter and a range of nutrients, has been applied as fertiliser across Europe for many decades. This practice has improved soil quality, reduced dependence on inorganic fertilisers and supported the circular use of nutrients. However, while the agricultural application of sewage sludge contributes to nutrient circularity, it is also recognised as an important source of secondary environmental pollution because it can contain numerous contaminants (Giwa et al., 2023). The concentration of pollutants and the associated environmental and health risks vary according to local conditions and the specific characteristics of the treated sludge (Buta et al., 2014; Pulkrabová et al., 2019; van den Berg et al., 2020). According to Eurostat, the EU livestock population is continuously declining, which implies that the volume of livestock manure available for fertilisation is also shrinking, even assuming optimal manure management systems (Oenema et al., 2007). Consequently, to maintain current nutrient (N–P–K) supply levels within a predominantly linear fertilisation regime, greater quantities of mineral and synthetic fertilisers will need to be produced.

1.2 Theoretical background for social acceptance

In this subchapter, we briefly summarise the theoretical background used throughout the investigation of social acceptance. These served as the basis for developing the survey and interview questions.

Much energy-related research highlights that technology acceptance is a key challenge for the successful implementation of emerging technologies (e.g. Beyer et al., 2018; Emmerich et al., 2020). In the literature on new technologies, “acceptability” is conceptualised as an attitudinal construct that refers to behavioural responses either in favour of or against a technology (Emmerich et al., 2020; Huijts et al., 2012). In this report, acceptance is explicitly examined in relation to new bio-based solutions that produce fertilisers from human excreta.

Beyond general acceptance, local opposition to the implementation of technologies is frequently described through the “not in my backyard” (NIMBY) phenomenon (Emmerich et al., 2020; Van Der Horst, 2007). As local residents tend to be particularly sensitive to risks that may affect them personally (Emmerich et al., 2020; Li et al., 2019; Terwel et al., 2011), this study focuses on identifying NIMBY-type attitudes associated with this often-stigmatised fertiliser resource.

Risk research repeatedly shows that laypeople may focus on relatively minor risks while overlooking others that pose more serious threats (Fischer et al., 1991). Against this backdrop, both the questionnaire survey—aimed at laypeople—and the interviews—conducted with stakeholders—explored concerns related to bio-based fertilisers derived from human excreta. Perceived risks of new food-related technologies, including health concerns or perceptions of “unnaturalness”, can increase neophobia, whereas highlighting health and sustainability benefits can attenuate these fears (Rodrigues Romano et al., 2025).

Trust represents another key determinant of attitudes and behaviour. It is a multifaceted concept (Mularska-Kucharek & Brzeziński, 2017) and has been widely examined across disciplines, yielding extensive theoretical and empirical insights (Bodor et al., 2020). Following Sztompka, trust can be defined as “betting on the possible future actions of others” (Sztompka, 1999, p. 25). As a subjective disposition, it develops through psychologically salient life experiences imbued with emotional and moral content (Bodor et al., 2020). Socially, trust facilitates various forms of cooperation (Sztompka, 1999). Social trust is shaped by people’s perceptions of the credibility, fairness, competence and transparency of institutions—often described as institutional trust (Rothstein & Stolle, 2008; You, 2012; Zmerli et al., 2007). Institutions play a key role in interpreting and responding to societal challenges (Bodor et al., 2020; Gifford, 2011). In our context, it is therefore crucial to identify which institutions are perceived as most trustworthy in introducing and disseminating new, safe bio-based fertilisation options.

The introduction of innovations as part of green transitions is resource-intensive. Research on environmental quality (e.g. Vicente et al., 2021), renewable energy (e.g. Baranyai & Varjú, 2017) and environmentally friendly products (Trivedi et al., 2015) frequently employs the constructs of “willingness to pay” (WTP) or “willingness to pay more” (WTPM) to assess individuals’ intentions to support a more sustainable environment. Understanding consumers’ WTP is essential because consumer demand drives production (Zeng et al., 2024) and thus shapes the potential uptake of new solutions. Moreover, given that innovations typically require substantial resources in their early phases, financial incentives are often necessary to scale sustainable options.

WTP is widely used to infer consumer preferences and the monetary valuation of goods and services. However, empirical evidence suggests that stated WTP does not always align with actual behaviour. It can be influenced by the retail environment (Boonchai et al., 2021), previous consumption habits (Wathieu, 2004) and the way products are presented, such as the “real-object advantage” phenomenon (Walsh-Snow et al., 2025). There is often a discrepancy between consumers’ favourable attitudes towards products (e.g. organic food) and their actual purchasing choices. This so-called intention–behaviour gap indicates that even when consumers report high WTP, this does not necessarily translate into a corresponding purchase, as other attributes (e.g., food origin) may carry greater weight in decision-making (Bernabéu et al., 2022).

Finally, communication channels are of fundamental importance for raising awareness and strengthening environmental consciousness. Identifying context- and place-specific information channels is therefore crucial for facilitating the diffusion of innovations and enhancing acceptance levels.

1.3 Current situation – Eurobarometer, ESS

Eurobarometer is the survey instrument used by the European Commission, the European Parliament, and other EU institutions and agencies to regularly monitor public opinion in Europe on issues related to the European Union and broader political and social matters. It generates high-quality, policy-relevant data that are widely used by public opinion specialists, academic researchers, the media and the general public¹.

The European Social Survey (ESS) is an academically driven, cross-national survey conducted across Europe since its inception in 2001. It is conducted biennially, with interviews conducted on newly drawn cross-sectional samples in each participating country².

We used both platforms to identify the antecedents of our topic, understand public opinion, and assess the level of acceptance of human-excreta based fertilisers. So far, none of the above platforms has conducted any surveys in this field; however, we think that an investigation into pro-environmental attitudes can provide a first picture of spatial differences across EU countries.

1.3.1 Attitudes toward environmental challenges

Environmental challenges have been a significant issue for decades. Eurobarometer asked about the opinions and attitudes on the environment from time to time, especially in topic-relevant surveys. However, pro-environmental attitudes not only emerge in topic-specific surveys but also in general surveys. The most recent general Eurobarometer aimed to reveal the current challenges and priorities of Europeans. The “EU challenges and priorities – November 2025” Eurobarometer survey explores how Europeans perceive the main problems facing the Union and the areas where they expect EU-level action. While the war in Ukraine remains the primary concern, climate change appears alongside irregular migration and the cost of living among the top challenges identified by respondents, confirming that environmental issues are now embedded in the core of the EU’s political agenda rather than treated as a niche topic. The findings suggest that citizens continue to see climate change as a structural, long-

¹ <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/about/eurobarometer>

² <https://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/about-ess>

term threat with implications for energy security, economic stability and social cohesion, and they expect the EU to play a leading role in addressing it. In this context, environmental and climate policies are viewed not only as ecological imperatives but also as essential components of a broader response to geopolitical tensions and economic uncertainty³.

Although there are several Eurobarometer surveys initiated by sectoral actors (including agriculture policy), it is difficult to find related surveys. There are Eurobarometers on resource efficiency in SMEs, in several years (e.g. in 2022, 2024); however, the questions are not related to farming.

The Special Eurobarometer 550 survey on Attitudes of Europeans towards the environment⁴ confirms that protecting the environment is a widely shared value, with very large majorities in all seven P2Green countries – Sweden, Germany, Spain, France, Greece, Italy and Hungary – stating that environmental protection is personally important. This is consistent with earlier Eurobarometer waves, which already showed figures in the 90% range for most Member States⁵.

Climate change, pollution (of air, water, and soil), and waste – particularly plastics and chemicals in everyday products – continue to dominate citizens' environmental concerns across these countries (Figure 2). However, their relative rankings and intensities differ. In the Northern and Western countries considered here, Sweden, Germany and France tend to exhibit the most consistently high levels of concern and a strong perception that environmental degradation and climate change are urgent problems that require structural responses. Swedish and Germans are particularly likely to emphasise the need for systemic changes in energy, transport and production systems, not only individual lifestyle adjustments, and to support ambitious EU-level action and regulatory measures. French respondents typically share strong concern about environmental risks, especially pollution and chemicals, and combine this with relatively high expectations regarding state intervention and social regulation.

In Southern Europe – Spain, Italy and Greece – concern about environmental problems is similarly high or even higher, but it is often more tightly intertwined with lived experiences of extreme weather, water scarcity, fires and local pollution. Respondents in these countries frequently highlight climate-related hazards (heatwaves, droughts, floods) and the degradation of local ecosystems, while also expressing concerns about affordability and social fairness in environmental policies. The survey results suggest that Spaniards and Italians are generally supportive of the green transition, but more likely than Swedes or Germans to stress that public authorities should ensure that costs do not disproportionately fall on low-income households. Greeks display very high levels of expressed concern and strong support for stronger environmental protection, yet also

³ <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/3380>

⁴ <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/3173>

⁵ https://www.mase.gov.it/portale/documents/d/guest/ebs_468_en-pdf

relatively high scepticism about the effectiveness and integrity of national institutions, which can complicate implementation.

Hungary broadly follows the EU pattern: a large majority of respondents say that environmental protection matters to them and that climate change is a serious problem; however, the survey indicates a somewhat more ambivalent picture regarding perceived individual efficacy and willingness to accept far-reaching lifestyle or cost-increasing changes. Compared with Northern and some Western Member States, Hungarians are more inclined to prioritise general cost-of-living concerns and energy affordability, and to emphasise technological solutions and external actors (EU, companies) rather than personal behavioural change as the primary drivers of environmental progress. This places Hungary closer to a cluster of Central and Eastern European countries where high abstract concern coexists with lower perceived capacity to act and more limited trust in environmental governance.

Across all seven countries, the survey documents a substantial gap between the widespread recognition of environmental problems and the extent to which citizens report engaging in more demanding pro-environmental behaviours. Everyday practices such as waste sorting, reducing single-use plastics and saving energy at home are widely reported, especially in Sweden, Germany and France, but costlier or more disruptive actions – such as major home renovations, switching to low-emission vehicles or systematically paying more for “green” products – are less common and more socially stratified. Southern countries and Hungary, where income constraints and social vulnerability are more salient, tend to show greater reluctance to accept substantial additional costs, even when concern is high.

QB6. Which of the following would you consider doing yourself to reduce the amount of waste? Please select all options that apply to you. (MULTIPLE ANSWERS POSSIBLE)
(% - The most mentioned answer by country)

Figure 2. Waste sorting in the EU

Source: Eurobarometer - Attitudes of Europeans towards the environment, 2024 - <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/3173>

Finally, the report underscores that across all seven countries, citizens expect public authorities to play a central role in steering the green transition, but the locus of that leadership differs. In Sweden and Germany, respondents are particularly supportive of strong EU-level standards and industrial policies, alongside national measures. In France, expectations of state intervention remain pronounced, including regulation of harmful products and support for green innovation. In Spain, Italy, Greece and Hungary, citizens emphasise both EU responsibility and the need for national governments to enforce rules fairly and to protect vulnerable groups, but concerns about governance quality and social equity are more prominent. Taken together, the findings suggest that while there is a broad cross-national consensus on the importance of environmental protection, country-specific constellations of concern, trust, economic vulnerability and policy expectations shape how support for climate and environmental measures can be mobilised in Sweden, Germany, Spain, France, Greece, Italy and Hungary.

A similar spatial difference can be seen when we investigate trust in pro-environmental attitudes, using data from Round 8 (2016) of the European Social Survey across 22 countries. Based on this survey, researchers present how generalised social trust shapes different dimensions of attitudes towards climate change in Europe. They distinguish between three key attitude components: (1) beliefs and concern about climate change, (2) perceived personal responsibility to reduce it, and (3) support for climate policy measures. Descriptive analysis shows that, while acceptance of the reality and anthropogenic nature of climate change and related concerns is high in most countries, there are apparent regional differences: Central and Eastern European societies tend to be more sceptical and display lower levels of personal responsibility and policy support than Western and Northern European countries (Bodor et al., 2020).

Using logistic regression at the individual level and comparative analysis at the macro level, the study finds that trust does not significantly affect climate change beliefs or concern, but it does have a robust positive effect on both the feeling of personal responsibility and support for climate policies. Moreover, in high-trust societies, the link between concern and action-oriented attitudes (responsibility and policy support) is substantially stronger. In contrast, in low-trust societies, high concern often coexists with weak responsibility and limited policy support. The paper concludes that cultivating a “culture of trust” is crucial for closing the concern–action gap and for enabling more effective collective responses to climate change (Bodor et al., 2020).

1.3.2 Attitudes towards the choice of foods

As HEDF might be used in agrifood production, it is worth having a look at the related European surveys and what people think about sustainable food and food security.

The Special Eurobarometer 505 survey “Making our food fit for the future – Citizens’ expectations” explores how Europeans understand and engage with sustainable food,

diets and food systems in the context of the Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy. It shows that when buying food, citizens still prioritise taste, safety and cost over explicitly environmental considerations, with only a minority citing environmental and climate impact as a main purchase criterion. At the same time, when asked what makes food “sustainable”, respondents most often highlight it being nutritious and healthy, produced with little or no pesticides, and affordable for all, while lower environmental and climate impact, local/short supply chains, high animal-welfare standards and minimal packaging are recognised but less prominent. A majority associate sustainable diets with eating a variety of foods, more fruit and vegetables, seasonal and local products, fewer pesticides and reduced food waste, and around two-thirds report that they eat a healthy and sustainable diet always or most of the time, albeit with large cross-country variation⁶.

Affordability and availability emerge as the key levers for wider adoption of sustainable diets: respondents most often say they would be helped by healthy, sustainable options being affordable and available where they usually shop, followed by clearer information on labels about environmental, health and social impacts. Europeans assign primary responsibility for making food systems sustainable to producers and food manufacturers, followed by national governments and, to a lesser extent, consumers and EU institutions. They express very strong support for public and private action to improve access to sustainable food, including compulsory sustainability information on labels, one common logo for healthy and sustainable food, stricter regulatory standards and more proactive EU action worldwide, while simultaneously judging current public efforts as insufficient. Concerns about food fraud centre on being misled about the true qualities of food, potential health risks, and the reliability of claims such as “organic” or origin labels, underlining the importance of transparency and trust for the transition to sustainable food systems⁷.

⁶ <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/2241>

⁷ <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/2241>

2 Description of the empirical investigations – Methods and research design

In this chapter, we describe the methods used to assess social acceptance of HEDF and how the empirical methods were implemented across the regions.

2.1 Surveys targeting everyday people in the 7 cases

To investigate social acceptance, online surveys were launched in the first year of the project in English and in the pilot regions' native languages (Swedish, Spanish, German), and in the second year in the follower regions (Italian, Hungarian, and Greek). In the French case, there is a delay; the survey is still underway. The aim was to achieve at least 50 responses in every case. The online link and QR code for the English version and, later, for the native versions were published on the P2Green Facebook and LinkedIn pages, as well as on the project's regular webpage. The links were also distributed by the consortium partners' own webpages and social media platforms. Altogether, we received 53 responses from the Swedish, 84 from the Spanish and 249 from the German pilot regions. Regarding the follower regions, we received 57 full responses from Greece, 52 from Italy, and 97 from Hungary. Unfortunately, to date, we have received only 31 full responses from France (Table 1); therefore, we decided not to include them in this report due to the low response rate. We do not think that it is a hiatus, because, about the acceptance in the Paris region, there is a separate deliverable (D3.3), for which the first interim report is already submitted, and the final report is due in M40, hence, the findings on acceptance can be found there.

We also have to emphasise the limitations of this survey, particularly its representativeness. As there was no existing resource for conducting a representative survey in the regions for this project, the main aim, which has been achieved, is to gain insights from the different areas, cultures, and their differences regarding the acceptance of bio-based fertilisers.

The questionnaire (see in the Annex) began with a demographic section, followed by a section of questions on the importance of various social issues. In this introductory block, not only general social problems but also environmental-related challenges were subject to opinion.

After two questions on openness to innovation were answered, the next block of the survey focused on trust, looking at which stakeholders people trusted the most. Perceived behavioural control was also detected after a question on attitude (c.f. Ajzen, 1991, p. 179), although it was not a factor this research aimed to reveal. These questions were followed by questions investigating the phenomena of NIMBY and WTP.

In the survey, two types of “locality” associated with the NIMBY phenomenon were examined. In one item, respondents were presented with a hypothetical scenario involving a plant located near their residence that produces fertiliser from human excreta. In the other, they were asked to consider a scenario in which a nearby park would be fertilised using this type of fertiliser. A 10-point Likert scale (1–10) was employed to measure acceptance and to assess the perceived value of these new technologies.

2.2 Focus groups in the 7 cases

Focus group interviews (see the guidance in the Annex) were conducted with stakeholders to reveal their experiences of social acceptance. Firstly, they were asked about their opinion on the acceptance of bio-based fertilisers by people in their country, and then we were curious about their views on farmers. We also asked them about their own opinions on using new solutions (like a separator toilet) in their own homes.

To avoid overloading stakeholders, we organise these focus groups in cooperation with WP4 (Building the governance framework) T4.2 (Co-create Strategies to empower and engage local businesses and relevant stakeholders) colleagues during their stakeholder engagement workshops for the pilots (M6-12) and Paris (M25), and with WP5 (Upscaling the impact) during their knowledge exchange and capacity building (T.5.3) workshops (M13-14) for the followers.

In each pilot region, seven participants were selected. In Hungary, we had 23 experts divided into 3 groups; in Italy, 3; and in Greece, 7. In the case of the Paris region, 6 stakeholders contributed to the workshop (Table 1), which included a section on social acceptance - comprising actors involved in the experiments (separator toilet manufacturers and fertiliser producers), potential users (farmers), researchers and representatives of water utilities and food processing companies. Owing to differences in context across cases, the composition of participants varied somewhat by region. The focus group interviews were conducted in the participants' native languages by representatives of the consortium partners, following a detailed interview guide. Responses were summarised, and the discussions were audio-recorded; these materials form the basis of the present analysis.

The online focus group interview was co-organised with the WP4 engagement workshop. The aim was to collect experiences, viewpoints, and engagement regarding the source separation developments in the refurbished area in Saint-Vincent-de-Paul and the use of urine-based fertilisers across different fields. The second part of the workshop focused on questions of governance and project acceptance.

2.3 Stakeholder Interviews in the 7 cases

Between January and March 2024, semi-structured interviews (see the questions in the Annex) were conducted with five additional stakeholders per pilot region, and between January 2024 and May 2025 in the follower regions and Paris region with four, with a particular effort to include experts from municipal administrations (Table 1). These interviews, which lasted approximately 30 minutes, were conducted online in English and included questions that had not been covered in the focus group discussions. Following a general set of items on attitudes towards the environment and climate change, the interview guide addressed NIMBY-related issues, trust, willingness to pay for community investments and perceived generational differences. The interviews also reflected on the findings of the questionnaire survey and focus group discussions, aiming to elaborate and deepen the insights provided by those respondents.

	Focus group interviews	Survey (questionnaire)	Semistructured interviews
Spain	7	84	5
Germany	7	249	5
Sweden	7	54	5
Greece	7	57	5
Hungary	23	97	4
Italy	3	52	4
France	6	31	4

Table 1: Number of people involved in each of the seven regions for each of the forms of data collection

3 Description of the results in the 7 cases

This chapter aims to describe the findings of the empirical investigations described above.

3.1 Results of the surveys

Hereby, we present the most important findings of the surveys (see the questions in the Annex) from the different countries. The aim here is not simply to present the results but also to emphasise the spatial differences.

The first questions aimed to ask the trust of people in different actors (private, government) and their actions (building new facilities, operation). Having a look at the institutional trust, we can see that people moderately trust companies in the private sector that build safe facilities (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Trust in private sector building safe facilities.

Note: Mean of evaluation on a 1 to 10 Likert scale where 1= strongly disagree and 10 =strongly agree.

However, when the question turned to the safe operation of private companies, people are generally more sceptical (Figure 4). In both cases, Italian respondents gave the lowest scores, while Hungarians gave the highest.

Figure 4: Trust in safe operation

Furthermore, what we can see is that in every case, people have less trust in the public sector, compared to the private sector. People are sceptical of governments and authorities, as they consider that they are failing to address their local needs (Figure 5) or make responsible decisions about introducing new technologies (Figure 6). The means in every case are less than in the responses on the private sector. As can also be seen, in the case of Hungary, people are much less trusting of the government than of private companies. The reason can be recent actions of the Hungarian government, when they attract huge investments in the battery sector without asking/consulting with local communities (c.f. Ricz & Éltető, 2025).

Trust in government/authorities - Consider the needs of local residents
(Mean)

Figure 5: Trust in government/authorities, whether they consider the needs of local residents in the six countries

Trust in government - responsible decision on introduction new technologies
(Mean)

Figure 6: Trust in government making responsible decisions on the introduction of new technologies in the six countries.

The "not in my backyard" (NIMBY) phenomenon was investigated through two questions. One question concerned how respondents felt about a plant being built nearby that processes human excreta into fertiliser, while the other asked how they felt about green areas and parks in their immediate vicinity being fertilised with fertiliser

made from human urine. In general, people in every country are more accepting of a green area fertilised with human-excreta-based fertiliser (Figure 7) than of a facility that processes human excreta to produce fertiliser (Figure 8). In spatial terms, there is a significant difference between the countries. The highest acceptance (the lowest NIMBY) is seen in Sweden and Germany, while the lowest acceptance (the highest NIMBY) is found in Hungary and Greece.

The reason can be twofold. On the one hand, these patterns largely follow pro-environmental behaviour (see the Eurobarometer analysis in this report). In these surveys, Sweden and Germany have the highest levels of pro-environmental attitudes, while Southern and Eastern countries have lower levels. On the other hand, some research reports that, besides socioeconomic conditions (c.f. Witkowska-Dabrowska et al., 2021), trust in entities also influences the phenomenon of NIMBY. Distrust can exacerbate NIMBY attitudes, while transparent and inclusive decision-making processes can help build trust and reduce opposition (Hu & Han, 2023; Konisky et al., 2021).

Figure 7: Acceptance of human excreta-based fertilised green area in the six countries.

Figure 8: Acceptance of facility processing human excreta-based excreta for fertiliser in the six countries.

Many people tend to feel cautious or uneasy when confronted with unfamiliar or novel things. . Therefore, it is essential to investigate their concern about the potential impacts of human excreta-based fertilisers. In the survey, smell, contamination of the environment and infection were asked as concerns. Respondents in general have the highest concern about smell (overall mean: 6,25), while they have the lowest concern about infection (overall mean: 5,04). The highest level of concern is found in Spain, Greece, and Hungary, while the lowest is in Sweden and Germany (Figures 9, 10, 11). In the literature, the number of studies on these concerns is limited. What can be found is that the concern or perception of smell/odour differs by region within a country (e.g. Cantone et al., 2017).

Globally, odour intensity is more regionally dependent than pleasantness, indicating that while the perception of how strong an odour is can vary widely, the basic hedonic perception (pleasant vs. unpleasant) is more consistent across cultures (Drnovsek et al., 2025).

Figure 9: The level of concern about smell in the six countries. (Mean)

Figure 10: The level of concern about the contamination of the environment in the six countries. (Mean)

Figure 11: The level of concern about the infection in the six countries. (Mean)

Willingness to pay (WTP) has also been addressed. We posed the following question: *Imagine, that there are two types of vegetables on the market. One is fertilised with cheap artificial fertiliser, the other (more expensive) with fertiliser made from human urine/waste-water. The latter, however, is 100% environmentally friendly, sustainable and follows the principles of a circular economy. How much more would you be willing to pay for this vegetable?* What can be seen is that willingness to pay shows significant spatial differences. Moving from North to South and East, WTP levels decrease (Figure 12). These spatial differences align with the Eurobarometer survey results on sustainable products (Figure 13).

Figure 12: Willingness to pay for a product fertilised by human excreta-based fertiliser in the six countries. (Rate (%) of people who are willing to pay more.)

Figure 13: Willingness to pay for sustainable products in the EU.

Source: Attitudes of Europeans towards the environment, 2024 - <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/3173>

The WTP phenomenon was examined from another perspective. We asked people what to choose in different scenarios. What would they choose in case all vegetables that are fertilised with different types of fertilisers have the same price (Figure 14), what if the cheapest is fertilised with human excreta-based fertiliser (Figure 15), and what if the human excreta-based fertiliser is the healthiest (Figure 16). Spatial difference is again on the spot. Swedish and German people are the most open to the new fertiliser, while, at the same price, Eastern and Southern European respondents prefer traditional manure fertilisers. When the price of human excreta-based fertiliser is lower than that of conventional fertilisers, people may be open to this solution and prefer it over others. The only exception is Hungary, where respondents still prefer the conventional animal manure. In Hungary, this phenomenon has changed only slightly, when a human-excreta-based fertilised product is the healthiest option.

Figure 14: Which of the following products is chosen once the products are fertilised with different fertilisers of different origins, in the case the price of the product is the same.

Figure 15: Which of the following products is chosen once the products are fertilised with different fertilisers of different origins, in the case that the cheapest is fertilised by human-excreta-based fertiliser?

Figure 16: Which of the following products is chosen once the products are fertilised with different fertilisers of different origins, in the case of human excreta-based fertiliser, which is the healthiest at the same price?

Comparative summary

The cross-country surveys reveal clear spatial gradients in trust, NIMBY-type acceptance, perceived risks and willingness to pay for human excreta-based fertilisers. Institutional trust is higher for the private than the public sector in all countries: respondents moderately trust private firms to build safe facilities but are more sceptical about their safe operation, with Italians giving the lowest and Hungarians the highest ratings; trust in governments is consistently lower, and in Hungary the gap between low governmental trust and relatively high private-sector trust is particularly pronounced, plausibly reflecting recent contested state-led investments. Acceptance patterns likewise differ by locality: across all cases, people are more comfortable with nearby green areas fertilised using human excreta-based products than with a processing facility sited near their homes, yet Sweden and Germany show the highest acceptance (lowest NIMBY), while Hungary and Greece show the lowest (highest NIMBY), aligning both with broader pro-environmental attitude profiles and with evidence that low trust amplifies local resistance. Risk perceptions focus most strongly on odour, followed by environmental contamination and infection, with concern highest in Spain, Greece and Hungary and lowest in Sweden and Germany. Finally, willingness to pay for vegetables fertilised with human excreta-based products declines from North to South and East, mirroring Eurobarometer patterns on sustainable consumption; scenario questions confirm that Swedes and Germans are most open even at equal prices, Southern and Eastern respondents prefer conventional manure unless human excreta-based options

are cheaper or clearly healthier, and Hungary remains the most resistant even under favourable price/health framing.

3.2 Results of the focus group and individual interviews

In this chapter, we present the most important findings of the interviews in the different case study regions.

3.2.1 Spain

According to the stakeholders, the acceptability of reclaimed water is strongly conditioned by the position and interests of the actors involved. In practice, farmers may be inclined to adopt this type of fertiliser, particularly because it can partly mitigate water scarcity in Andalusia and, more broadly, in Spain. By contrast, consumers tend to be more hesitant. Although this alternative fertilisation method is environmentally sustainable, it cannot be marketed as organic under current regulations. In a context where products that are not certified as organic are often viewed with suspicion by the stakeholders. One of the stakeholders added that everything which is called waste, even “criminalised”. This presents a significant challenge.

In light of these concerns, stakeholders identified odour as a potentially major source of disturbance, alongside anxieties about pharmaceutical residues. Water quality is a highly sensitive issue throughout Spain, which is why political actors generally avoid terms such as “residue” or “waste”. Consequently, in the Spanish context, policymakers often prefer not to use the term “wastewater” when describing new bio-based innovative processes such as the one examined in this study.

When discussing social differentiation, respondents primarily emphasised generational divides and the digital gap, which may hinder rapid access to reliable information. They also highlighted a perceived generational challenge: some younger people are seen as asserting a strong sense of entitlement to choose freely what they use or reject. This attitude may influence both the introduction and siting of new bio-based innovative solutions.

The interviews further identified factors that could facilitate wider diffusion and public acceptance. For instance, using reclaimed water derived from wastewater contributes to the protection of water basins, and such solutions can be framed as analogous to free-range egg production in the sense that they support more sustainable practices. The use of these bio-based solutions is also consistent with the idea of short supply chains. Moreover, as one interviewee noted, this approach is not fundamentally different from the long-standing use of conventional livestock manure, which may also contain

pharmaceutical residues yet rarely prompts public concern. A key observation was that wastewater should be regarded not as waste but as a resource.

Stakeholders considered local governments and municipalities to be the most credible and influential actors for communicating about these innovations. (It is not in contradiction with the above, where trust in government was assessed low, because the low level of trust related to central governments in most cases.) Local wastewater treatment companies were likewise seen as highly trusted. In terms of communication channels, social media and local newspapers were identified as the most important means of disseminating information.

This implies that effective communication strategies should be anchored at the local level, with municipalities and utilities acting as visible “front faces” of the innovation rather than relying solely on national institutions or project partners. Prioritising locally embedded channels and messengers can help translate technical information into locally meaningful narratives, reduce perceptions of risk and distance, and create opportunities for dialogue and feedback. In practical terms, this points to the need for co-developed communication campaigns, regular updates via local media, and targeted engagement activities that leverage the existing trust placed in local authorities and service providers.

3.2.2 Sweden

In the Swedish pilot region, P2Green researchers examine the conversion of urine into pellets and their subsequent use as fertiliser. As one interviewee noted, the use of urine in agriculture is not new in Sweden, which may contribute to higher levels of social acceptance (as also reflected in the survey results). Similar to the Spanish region, stakeholders reported that farmers tend to be more willing to adopt such innovative solutions than food processors or consumers. They further observed that the more processed the end product, the more acceptable the underlying bio-based innovation appears to be. One stakeholder suggested that this may partly be due to the fact that many young people in Sweden are no longer fully aware of how meals and their ingredients are produced. The interviews also underscored the need to clearly distinguish between fertilisation and pesticide use in public communication, as these concepts are not necessarily well understood by laypeople. Among stakeholders’ concerns, pharmaceutical residues emerged as the primary issue.

A key advantage of the solution in Sweden is the local availability of the “recycled” material. Stakeholders indicated that the introduction of some form of sustainability certification could further facilitate the wider uptake of products fertilised with urine. As in other regions, interviewees emphasised that this fertiliser is comparable in many respects to conventional farmyard manure. They also suggested that a sewage tax could serve as an additional policy lever to encourage the adoption of this new solution.

Swedish stakeholders considered the companies involved in the innovation process to have the main responsibility for providing transparent information to the public about investments in new technologies. Local governments were likewise seen as important actors in supporting the diffusion of alternative fertilisation practices. Social media and local newspapers were identified as two particularly significant channels for disseminating information about these solutions.

3.2.3 Germany

In the German case study region, stakeholders generally expressed comparatively few reservations about products fertilised with nutrients derived from human excreta. The dominant argument was that this form of nutrient application is analogous to conventional animal-based fertilisation. Generalised trust was also perceived to be high; as one interviewee remarked, if a product is available in a supermarket, consumers tend to assume that it has been thoroughly checked and is therefore trustworthy. At the same time, another interviewee contended that such products should not be marketed explicitly as being fertilised with human excreta-based manure, as society is not yet prepared for this level of transparency, and only a small minority of consumers would be interested in how the product was produced or farmed. It was also emphasised that the issue at stake concerns agricultural practices rather than the product itself, given that organic products are likewise fertilised. The question is whether such information needs to be communicated to consumers at all. In this regard, focus group participants converged on the view that such details should be disclosed in the context of direct sales via farm shops, but not necessarily in supermarkets.

Regarding specific concerns, German stakeholders primarily highlighted the potential presence of hormone residues. Where possible, they indicated a preference for promoting products fertilised with this type of manure as organic, provided regulatory frameworks allow it. Another important message identified by the interviewees is that the use of dry or compost toilets (c.f. Roach et al., 2015) constitutes a form of water conservation. This is an increasingly salient issue in Germany, as one participant emphasised.

In the German case, municipalities were seen as the most credible actors for supporting the dissemination of new fertilisation solutions. Non-governmental organisations were also considered important, particularly in their monitoring function and their capacity to react quickly to emerging issues. Social media and local newspapers were identified as the main channels through which information about such innovative solutions is likely to spread.

3.2.4 Greece

In Greece, the focus group participants rate general openness to new ideas at a moderate level, describing people as initially unreceptive but emphasising that proper information and good examples can significantly increase acceptance. Experts agree that, without explanation, products labelled as fertilised with human excreta-based nutrients would likely face considerable consumer reluctance. Some consumers might pay more for products labelled as environmentally friendly, but explicit references to “human excreta” or “wastewater” are seen as sensitive and potentially off-putting, even if comparable practices (e.g. manure fertilisation) are widely accepted and positively associated with small-scale farming.

For farmers, the Greek focus group highlights a more pragmatic stance: they see no fundamental reason to refuse such fertilisers if quality and yield are assured and costs are not significantly higher than for conventional inputs. The likelihood that farmers would use these fertilisers is relatively cautious but not dismissive, and experts stress that cost, yield performance, and certification (e.g. a “green” or quality label) would be crucial to uptake. They also call for more agricultural research and long-term trials, as well as monitoring, to stabilise product characteristics and build confidence. Consumers’ willingness to buy labelled products is lower, whereas experts themselves rate their own willingness substantially higher, indicating a gap between expert and lay acceptance. Willingness to retrofit buildings with new sanitation systems is very low, reflecting cost barriers and infrastructural constraints.

The Greek semi-structured interviews underscore strong NIMBY dynamics: respondents think local citizens would be most concerned about odour, noise, increased truck traffic, air pollution, and potential contamination of coastal waters, especially in seaside communities. At the same time, they see clear opportunities: if farmers can obtain cheaper or more reliable fertiliser, and if waste is managed better, such investments are perceived as “very good” and beneficial, with potential job creation and local economic gains.

On trust and communication, Greek interviewees emphasise the primary role of local government, often in partnership with investors, in organising public events and explaining projects; long-standing mayors with good track records can be powerful facilitators of acceptance. NGOs are generally seen as weak in many localities, though this varies by topic and scale. Social media, local newspapers, public events and face-to-face interactions are described as the most important channels, and university professors or experts are regarded as particularly credible. Generational differences are pronounced: younger farmers and citizens are more open to innovation and to the EU Green Deal agenda, while farmers over 50 are portrayed as attached to established chemical practices and more difficult to convince.

In sum, the Greek case indicates conditional openness: farmers can be convinced if economic and agronomic conditions are favourable and if robust evidence and certification are provided; consumers are more cautious, especially when confronted with explicit references to human excreta. Social acceptance depends heavily on trusted local political leadership, clear and tailored communication, visible local benefits, and explicit management of environmental and nuisance concerns.

3.2.5 Italy

In Italy, the focus group depicts society as rather cautious toward innovation. Experts expect that if food labels explicitly stated that fertilisation derived from human excreta, opposition from consumers would likely emerge, despite the absence of any current requirement to disclose fertiliser sources. They also stress that the term “bio-fertiliser” is misleading in this context because the stabilisation process and resulting pure urea product would not qualify under organic farming rules. This shows that the public perceives “bio-fertilisers” as fertilisers suitable for organic farming and not as ones that originate from biological sources, corroborating the confusion around these terms and the need for clearer communication of terms and legislative frameworks. Farmers, by contrast, are considered much more pragmatic: the likelihood that they would use such fertilisers is assessed as high, provided the products are cheaper or at least competitive with conventional fertilisers and agronomically reliable. Financial incentives are seen as necessary if the cost cannot match that of existing products. Willingness to retrofit buildings for separate collection is low, reinforcing the view that infrastructure change is more acceptable in new developments than through costly retrofits.

The semi-structured interviews deepen this picture by highlighting NIMBY concerns plus strong expectations of participation. Italian stakeholders underline that residents tend to fear pollution, odour, noise, visual and landscape impacts, and potential reductions in property values when new treatment facilities are proposed – a classic NIMBY pattern. Interviewees repeatedly insist that citizens should not only be informed but also actively involved in co-planning and co-designing such projects. They argue that acceptance is more likely if people perceive themselves as beneficiaries and co-owners of the innovation rather than passive recipients.

Interestingly, the Italian interviews suggest a somewhat higher trust in private companies than in public administrations when it comes to communication: company communication is seen as clearer, more direct, and better adapted to citizens via social media, apps and videos, whereas public administration is associated with formal, technical language that many people find difficult to understand. At the same time, respondents stress that Italy is characterised by information gaps and limited transparency, which foster uncertainty and scepticism.

Despite these barriers, some interviewees underline that, if citizens are given adequate knowledge and skills, they need not be afraid of such investments, which are framed as opportunities for local economic and social development and for advancing circular economy goals. Gender and generational divides in broader Italian society are mentioned, but more as background context than as direct drivers of acceptance; they point to the need for differentiated communication strategies across age groups and social positions.

Overall, the Italian material suggests high farmer acceptance conditional on cost and agronomic performance; cautious but potentially persuadable citizens; and a strong emphasis on participatory processes, clear communication and visible local benefits to secure broader social acceptance.

3.2.6 Hungary

The Hungarian focus group portrays moderate openness to innovation, with experts emphasising that society is generally cautious and that openness is strongly generational: younger people are more receptive, while older cohorts are more resistant to change. Rural populations are described as conservative and habit-driven, which makes the introduction of unfamiliar sanitation and fertilisation concepts challenging. Interviewees similarly highlight a strong NIMBY reflex around new facilities; “people oppose almost everything today”, especially where there have been previous negative experiences or insufficient environmental impact assessment and communication.

Regarding acceptance of fertilisers derived from human excreta, experts expect gradual, niche-based adoption. They anticipate that early use will appear in specific micro-regions and special contexts, with social acceptance “cascading” only if pilots are successful. Farmers are considered pragmatically open as long as the product is licensed and cost-effective; in villages, nutrient-improving products of sludge origin are already used without major controversy. The average likelihood that farmers would use such fertilisers is moderate, with price and regulatory clarity as decisive criteria. For consumers, however, experts are sceptical: willingness to buy products explicitly labelled as fertilised with nutrients from human excreta is relatively low, and several participants stressed that such labelling might “scare away everybody”.

At the same time, there is a small but growing segment of environmentally conscious households that could be targeted, especially if products are framed as “circular” or “eco” rather than linked to “wastewater”. NIMBY and household-level changes represent further barriers: willingness to modify homes to accommodate new sanitation interfaces is low, with experts stressing cost, habit, and lack of perceived benefit as obstacles.

Semi-structured interviews confirm that trust and credible communication are central. Respondents emphasise the need for joint communication by local governments, civil

society organisations and, where possible, “correct” politicians; investors alone are considered self-interested and therefore not fully trusted. Social media (including local environmental Facebook groups), face-to-face events and school-based civic activities are seen as the most effective information channels. Interviewees frame acceptance less as a generational issue and more as a matter of cultural norms and prior experience: where people have seen transparent, well-managed environmental investments, resistance is lower; where communication was poor or irregular, opposition is strong.

Overall, in the Hungarian case, farmers’ conditional acceptance contrasts with assumed consumer reluctance, and social acceptance hinges on cost, regulatory simplicity, careful framing (circularity rather than “waste”), and credible, multi-actor communication.

3.2.7 France

The Service Technique Eau et Assainissement (STEA), responsible for managing wastewater networks in the City of Paris, was hesitant about managing the future urine collection network and the treatment plant on the Saint-Vincent-de-Paul (SVDP) site, as it had no experience in the matter. The City of Paris, therefore, decided to award a public contract in 2026 to initially delegate management of the network and the plant to an external service provider. The long-term plan would be to train STEA agents so that management of the system could be reinternalized within the City of Paris in the future.

There are also plans to award a contract to raise awareness of the issue among different stakeholders. One of the water agencies (providers) in the region also provides funding for user awareness and support initiatives because they consider it an important aspect.

The idea regarding the fertiliser to be produced in SVDP is to use it internally in the City of Paris, at its «Centre de Production Horticole de Rungis » (Centre de production horticole (CPH) - Horticultural Production Centre of Rungis), and possibly on green lawns in Paris. A first series of experiments with the Aurin® urine-based fertiliser, which interests the City of Paris notably for its concentrated and stabilised aspects, was carried out by Direction des Espaces verts et de l’Environnement (DEVE) agents in the CPH in 2023, to test its agronomic effectiveness on different types of plantations. A second series of experiments began in 2025 and will continue in 2026, with the goal of testing the fertiliser on plants in nurseries and on green lawns.

Questions were raised initially by the staff towards the efficiency of the urine fertiliser, and a few reluctances about using it. Afterwards, when the efficiency results came in, the staff were surprised as some of the results were very good on certain plantations, but less satisfactory on others. When they held the meeting to present the results, most of them were keen to continue and diversify the trials.

Another positive example could be seen in a workshop organised by a Paris stakeholder. During the workshops [organised with the panel of future residents to raise awareness], the workshop organiser brought along biscuits fertilised with urine. Packets of biscuits were handed out. At the start of the workshop, people didn't touch the packets. Then, after the workshop and the explanations, people tasted the biscuits and left with packets.

The prospect of installing new types of source-separating toilets in private and public housing was generally well-accepted by developers and landlords, knowing that they did not have the possibility to refuse, as this project was part of the specifications they had to meet for the SVDP neighbourhood. Developers' and landlords' concerns focused on the technical and societal aspects (toilet efficiency, odour issues, user acceptance, etc.) and the financial aspects of the project (the price of these specific toilets being higher than classical ones). However, l'Agence de l'Eau Seine-Normandie (AESN) subsidies made it possible to minimise the investments required by developers and landlords for the project.

A survey was conducted in 2024 by the City of Paris in conjunction with the OCAP (programme) research team (ENPC/CEREMA) among a panel of future SVDP residents to assess the acceptance of urine diversion flush toilets and the issues surrounding them. It reveals a very good level of acceptance of the project, which is probably linked to the awareness-raising actions previously carried out on the subject by Paris Métropole Aménagement P&MA and the City of Paris. Indeed, several information and awareness-raising workshops have been carried out for the panel of pre-identified future residents in recent years. An awareness-raising video was also produced. As one of the stakeholders indicated, the survey conducted among panels of pre-identified future residents revealed that the separate toilet project with urine collection is generally welcomed with enthusiasm by future residents.

3.2.8 A comparative summary

Across the seven country cases, several common patterns of social acceptance emerge. In all contexts, farmers are generally more open than consumers to the use of fertilisers derived from human excreta, provided that agronomic performance and costs are competitive with conventional inputs. Consumers, by contrast, tend to be cautious or reluctant, especially when fertilisation practices are made explicitly visible on labels or framed in terms of "human excreta" or "wastewater", and when products cannot be certified as organic. Concerns about odour, pharmaceutical or hormone residues, and potential impacts on water quality are recurrent, as are NIMBY-type reactions around new facilities and a very low willingness to retrofit existing buildings with new sanitation technologies. At the same time, stakeholders in all countries see scope for improving acceptance by reframing wastewater as a resource, drawing analogies to familiar

practices such as livestock manure or other sustainable products, and using certification, demonstration trials and locally available “recycled” nutrients as selling points. Across cases, trust in local public authorities, utilities and/or companies, and the use of social media, local newspapers and targeted workshops are viewed as crucial for effective communication and for building confidence in these bio-based innovations.

The country narratives differ mainly in the specific social, institutional and discursive contexts in which these common issues play out. In Spain, acceptance is tightly interwoven with concerns over water scarcity and water quality, and political actors actively avoid terms such as “waste” or “wastewater”, while generational and digital divides are seen as potential barriers to informed debate. In Sweden, prior familiarity with urine use, strong emphasis on local resource circularity and the possibility of instruments such as a sewage tax create a comparatively favourable starting point, with companies expected to communicate transparently. In Germany, high generalised trust and the perception that supermarket products are already well controlled underpin relatively few reservations, though hormone residues remain a concern and transparency is seen as more appropriate in direct-sale channels than in mass retail. In Greece and Italy, NIMBY dynamics are particularly pronounced, linked to fears of odour, traffic, landscape and coastal impacts, but Italian stakeholders place strong emphasis on co-planning and co-design, and report greater trust in company communication than in public administration. In Hungary, resistance is framed as rooted in conservative rural norms, past negative experiences and generally low willingness to change household infrastructure, with a small environmentally conscious niche seen as a potential entry point. The French case stands out by focusing on internal municipal use and on future residents of a new neighbourhood, where structured awareness-raising, pilot trials and financial support for new toilets have produced relatively high and even enthusiastic acceptance among key user groups.

From the interviews, we summarised the most important concerns (Table 2), the key actors who must participate in the communication (Table 3), and the potential selling points (Table 4) in each case study region to increase social acceptance of innovations. (In the tables below, “+” means the given issue appeared, “-“ means that there is a strong opposition against, while empty cells mean that the issue did not occur during the interviews.)

	SWE	ESP	GER	GRE	ITA	HUN	FRA
Smell		+		+	+		
Quality of water		+					
Pharmaceuticals	+	+				+	
Noise	+			+			
Aesthetic/visual pollution	+			+	+		+
Hormons			+				
Heavy metal						+	

Table 2: Concerns of stakeholders

	SWE	ESP	GER	GRE	ITA	HUN	FRA
Investors	+	+	+		+		+
Regional/national government		+				-	
Local government/municipality	+	+	+		+	+	+
Waste treatment company		+					
NGOs			+	-			
"Label"						+	
Expert				+			

Table 3: Actors – who should communicate the solution to the general public

	SWE	ESP	GER	GRE	ITA	HUN	FRA
Surface water protection		+	+	+			
Part of a short value chain		+					+
It is a local resource	+	+				+	+
Similar to free-range egg		+					
Similar to an organic/sustainable product			+	+		+	
Similar to fertil. with manure	+	+					+
Recycled material	+						
Certification							
Education on the use of fertilisation	+						
Introduction of sewage fee							
Incentivisation					+		
Circular product						+	

Table 4: Selling points

4 Recommendations and a toolbox for improvement

Based on the above-described findings, we present here the measures that may be suitable for raising awareness of the use of human excreta-based fertiliser, the acceptance of its use, and the acceptance of agrifood and further processed products. The tools presented here are not only presented but also tested, and we provide the feedback as well.

Besides the traditional communication tools (such as video (see its experience above in the French case), leaflets, online descriptions) that can play an important role in increasing social acceptance of innovative fertilisers, we hereby present other tools that can provide further help in this.

4.1 Field visit as a tool

Besides a similar geographical situation, different countries and regions can be at different stages of technological and innovation development. It partly depends on a region's economic performance and partly on its technological traditions. Hence, if someone is in a lower stage of innovation, this country or region can learn from those who are on a better stage (Figure 17). "The European Innovation Scoreboard provides a comparative assessment of the Research and Innovation performance of EU Member States, other European countries, and global competitors. It helps countries assess the relative strengths and weaknesses of their national innovation systems and identify challenges that need to be addressed." Hence, this can be a tool to help to understand the difference in innovation among different countries: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard_en

Figure 17. Innovation scoreboard in the EU in 2025.

Source: <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-law-and-publications/publication-detail/-/publication/c102236e-66b2-11f0-bf4e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

4.1.1 Why field visits matter for social acceptance and implementation

Field visits constitute a high-value instrument for accelerating both knowledge transfer and social learning in the deployment of circular, sanitation-linked innovations such as human excreta-derived fertilisers (HEDF). In many regions, acceptance barriers are not primarily driven by lack of abstract concern for the environment, but by uncertainty, perceived risk and low trust, particularly when the innovation is associated with sensitive objects (urine, faeces, wastewater) and with “nearby” infrastructure (classic NIMBY dynamics). A field visit directly addresses these barriers by creating an opportunity for stakeholders to engage with the innovation in its material and operational reality—observing equipment, processes, hygiene protocols, monitoring routines, odour management, and end-products (Figure 18).

Figure 18.: Field visit at the German Goldmeier site.

As seen in the French case, field visits to see (and maybe try) the solutions (dry or separating toilets) are an essential part of understanding how they work and what their impacts are. Field visits are crucial not only for consumers and citizens but also for experts

This is also true when an innovation (or policy) is transferred from one place to another (Marsden & Stead, 2011; Stead, 2012; Varjú, 2022). This is also supported by other research projects (e.g., H2020 REPAIR), which emphasise the site visit as a key factor

for successful knowledge transfer⁸. Other research experience also emphasises the importance of the field visit. For instance, public engagement strategies for environmental projects, such as carbon capture, emphasise the importance of addressing local stakeholders' concerns and involving them in the process to gain social acceptance and support (Mulyasari et al., 2021).

Field visits are especially important where innovations involve tacit knowledge and context-specific practices that are hard to communicate through documents alone. For example, the “safety” of a nutrient-recycling chain is not only a matter of regulatory compliance but also of routines: how collection is organised, how cross-contamination risks are minimised, how operators respond to incidents, how odour is managed, and how outputs are tested and documented. These aspects are often best understood through in-situ demonstration, where participants can ask technical questions, inspect key control points, and compare “what is written” with “what is done”. In this sense, field visits support implementation by making the innovation legible not as an abstract concept but as a functioning socio-technical system (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Field visit in Gotland at the cement factory, where waste heat is used for drying out the urine.

⁸ <https://h2020repair.eu/project-results/knowledge-transfer-handbook/>

4.1.2 Field visits as a mechanism of knowledge transfer and learning

From a learning perspective, field visits support knowledge transfer in at least four complementary ways:

Experiential and multi-sensory learning

Many acceptance concerns (e.g., odour, hygiene, noise, visual impacts) are fundamentally experiential. A field visit enables participants to verify these aspects directly and to anchor their judgements in observation rather than speculation. This is particularly relevant for addressing stigma-related perceptions and clarifying the distinction between the treatment process and the agricultural product, which stakeholders frequently noted lay audiences can conflate.

Situated learning and translation to local contexts

Knowledge about circular sanitation solutions is not universally transferable as a “plug-and-play” model; it needs to be translated into local infrastructure, governance arrangements, agricultural practices, and cultural meanings. Field visits facilitate situated learning by allowing participants to identify which elements are context-dependent (e.g., logistics, regulations, farming systems, communication strategies) and which are generalisable. This supports more realistic upscaling pathways and helps avoid misalignment between technological design and local feasibility.

Social learning and coalition-building

Field visits create structured spaces for dialogue among heterogeneous actors—utilities, municipalities, technology providers, farmers, food processors, researchers and civil society—who often hold different problem framings and risk sensitivities. Shared observation acts as a common reference point (“we have all seen the same system”), reducing interpretive divergence and enabling more productive deliberation about trade-offs. This can strengthen cross-sectoral coalitions and generate a more coordinated narrative for local communication, which is essential where institutional trust is fragile.

Trust-building through transparency and demonstrability

In contexts where trust influences acceptance, field visits can operate as a credibility device. Seeing monitoring protocols, laboratory testing regimes, operator competence and accountability arrangements can increase confidence in both the technology and the institutions behind it. Importantly, the trust effect is not automatic; it depends on whether the visit demonstrates transparency (including acknowledgement of limitations) and provides opportunities for questioning, critique and clarification.

4.1.3 Field visits as communication and narrative infrastructure

Field visits also function as an upstream communication intervention: they generate credible, locally grounded stories and visual materials that can be reused in public-facing communication. Participants often become “messengers” within their organisations and communities, translating complex processes into accessible language. This is particularly valuable in settings where stakeholders identified municipalities, utilities and local media as key channels. Field visits can therefore be understood as an investment in narrative infrastructure: they help establish shared frames such as “wastewater as a resource”, “closing nutrient loops”, “local water protection”, and “safe, regulated treatment”, while avoiding terminology that triggers disgust or misunderstanding (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Field visit at the waste water treatment site in Axaquria, Spain.

4.1.4 Practical design principles for effective field visits

To maximise learning outcomes, field visits should be treated as a structured intervention rather than a site tour. Three elements are critical:

- **Before the visit:** clarify objectives (e.g., risk concerns to address; transferability questions), provide a short briefing pack (process overview, key safeguards, glossary), and collect participants’ expectations and concerns (e.g., via a short pre-visit questionnaire).

- **During the visit:** use a guided pathway that follows the value chain (collection → treatment → quality assurance → end-use), integrate “stop points” for Q&A, and explicitly address the issues most linked to acceptance (odour, residues, hygiene, governance responsibilities, monitoring).
- **After the visit:** conduct a structured debrief (what surprised participants; what conditions would enable uptake at home; what risks remain), capture concrete lessons learned, and translate these into actionable recommendations for local implementation and communication (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Practical design for an effective field visit.

Where in-person visits are not feasible, virtual field visits (e.g., 360° video or guided digital walkthroughs) can preserve part of the learning value—particularly for demonstrating process steps and mitigation measures—although they generally have lower capacity to resolve sensory concerns (especially odour) and therefore should be complemented by other trust-building measures (see Chapter 4.2).

4.1.5 Feedback

The way field visits are curated and managed can significantly influence social acceptance, either positively by fostering genuine engagement or negatively by reinforcing stereotypes. Therefore, in addition to organising field visits in the P2GreenN project to provide first-hand experience to all the experts involved and to those unfamiliar with the topic, we surveyed to gather feedback from stakeholders on what they have learned and how to improve the field visits (Questions of the field visit can be found in the Annex.) 45 members of the consortium filled out the survey.

Participants in field visits think that direct experience is most important for understanding whether a process has any noise (Q8.b). Smell (Q8.a) is only third in the list. Respondents also think that a field visit is very useful for decision makers, except for national-level ones.

What is interesting from the field visit survey is that people participating in different field visits think differently about the usefulness of different aspects. For instance, people participating in the German field assess the highest importance of experiencing smell, compared to the visits of the other two fields (Q8.a). The reason can be that in the German case, two sites with faecal processing were visited, while in Gotland and Axaquria, faecal processing was not in the field. Another example can be seen in the case of the water-saving question (Q8.k). Field visitors from Gotland think that a less serious issue is to solve this challenge by conducting field visits to compare visitors from German and Spanish fields (Figure 22). This can also be explained by geography.

Figure 22: Opinion of field visitors about the importance of a field visit to experience the importance of water scarcity. Note: Mean of the 1-10 Likert scale responses, where 1 means – It did not reduce doubts at all, while 10 means – It reduced the doubts totally.

The above-mentioned feedback draws our attention to the importance of case specificity and geography. Field visits cannot only contribute to a better understanding of a new solution or process, but the geography of the field and the specificities of the process shown can also have an effect on the understanding.

4.2 Online field visit

Virtual field trips have been developed to overcome logistical challenges, providing an immersive experience that can enhance engagement and learning, which may indirectly promote social acceptance (Eiris et al., 2022). In the P2Green project, colleagues in WP1 (Blueprinting the regional clusters) elaborated 360° tours/augmented realities through the pilot facilities, as part of Deliverable 1.1, due in M36. (Figure 23. More details on this can be found there.) This tool enables stakeholders to understand the facilities that produce fertilisers, thereby supporting increased acceptance. The tool is suitable for partly substituting the field visit, except for experiencing the potential odour.

German Pilot Region

Eberswalde

Figure 23. Starting screen of the augmented reality of the Eberswalde site

The tours will be included in Deliverable 1.1, via the following link, and they will be available on the P2Green website as well: <https://p2green.eu/discover-p2greens-pilot-regions-and-learn-how-nutrient-recovery-works-in-practice/>

4.3 Short description and main aims of the videogame

Video games activate brain reward systems, promoting cognitive learning and social interaction. This fosters social acceptance and emotional engagement, integrating principles of neurocommunication with immersive experiences (Barrientos-Báez et al., 2025). Gamification can make the learning process engaging and motivating. By incorporating elements such as feedback, awards, achievements, and competitive elements, video games can encourage users to learn about and accept new practices (Helmefalk & Rosenlund, 2020; Hsu, 2022; Venturi et al., 2025). Video games can influence behaviour by providing interactive and immersive experiences. For example, games that simulate the benefits of using human excreta-based fertilisers can help users understand and appreciate their value. Serious games designed for educational purposes can raise awareness about the benefits and safety of using human excreta as fertiliser. These games can provide first-hand experiences and facilitate discussions on the topic (Calvo-Morata & Fernández-Manjón, 2023; McConville et al., 2023; Shliakhovchuk, 2024). Video games can reduce the psychological distance associated with environmental issues, making them more relatable and urgent. This can be particularly effective in changing perceptions about using human excreta-based fertilisers (Bekoum Essokolo & Robinot, 2022).

To sum up, video games, through their engaging and interactive nature, can play a significant role in increasing social acceptance of human excreta-based fertilisers. By leveraging gamification techniques, reducing psychological distance, promoting empathy, and providing practical demonstrations, video games can help change perceptions and behaviours towards these sustainable innovations. That is why the P2Green project elaborated a video game to fulfil the above purposes. The video game (Figure 24) itself is Deliverable 3.5; however, here, we can also shortly present it.

Figure 24. The opening screen of the video game.

P2Green: Turning Waste into Green Wealth is an interactive web-based game that raises awareness about the nutrient cycle and shows how human waste can be turned into a valuable resource for sustainable agriculture. Through an engaging and interactive experience, players learn about the circular economy and the environmental benefits of reusing biological waste as a resource (Figure 25).

Figure 25. The two sets of the video game.

In the game, players take on the role of planners and visionaries tasked with transforming a barren, grey landscape into a thriving green environment (Figure 26).

Figure 26. German landscape is under planning in the video game.

They progress by engaging with a series of educational modules and quizzes (Figure 27) that introduce them to the core principles of the P2Green project and its sustainable solutions. Correct answers earn points that unlock innovations developed within the P2Green framework, which can then be applied to the digital environment. With each improvement, the virtual world evolves: what begins as a desolate, heavily industrialised terrain gradually transforms into a lively, organic landscape. As players advance through the levels, they move from rural to semi-rural and eventually to urban settings. In each stage, they make strategic decisions that shape their surroundings, selecting and implementing P2Green's solutions to restore and regenerate the land.

Figure 27. A quiz question in the video game.

The game aims to educate its audience about the benefits of using biological waste as fertiliser, promote behavioural change toward sustainable living, and highlight the importance of circular economy principles, all while ensuring an enjoyable and motivating gameplay experience. P2Green is designed primarily for teenagers and young adults, educators, and anyone interested in environmental issues. Through play, participants come to understand the vital role of urine and faeces in sustainable practices, recognising how even small actions can lead to meaningful environmental improvements.

The video game can be found via this link: <https://play.unity.com/en/games/34a773de-bc0b-4f9f-84e2-f93a2db6a541/p2green-v21>

The learning process covers key topics such as the circular economy, the nutrient cycle, nature-based solutions, and waste composition. Players explore innovative systems, including urine diversion toilets, neighbourhood-scale processing stations, urban

gardens, green living walls, and membrane bioreactors in waste treatment plants. By integrating this knowledge into the game's progression, *P2Green: Turning Waste into Green Wealth* combines learning and creativity, empowering players to see how sustainable practices and thoughtful planning can drive positive environmental change.

Feedback

During the implementation of the project, a dedicated workshop was held (during the Budapest consortium meeting) to provide feedback. The input gathered during the game testing session provided valuable insights into opportunities to improve both gameplay design and user engagement. Participants suggested that the worldbuilding scenarios should more closely align with the pilot project regions to better support the game's educational and awareness-raising objectives.

The current point system could be refined to more accurately represent differences in investment levels across technologies, helping players understand the strategic trade-offs involved in resource allocation. Additionally, introducing an indicator system to visualise the impact of these investments would offer players more immediate and meaningful feedback on their decisions.

The question set should also be restructured to incorporate a clear progression of difficulty levels, promoting a more balanced learning curve, and sustaining user engagement. Furthermore, educational content will be added before the quiz to provide context by explaining the sanitation value chain, and additional information will be included before each scenario to clarify the specific conditions of each pilot region.

Finally, improving the user's flow by allowing direct access to the worldbuilding or scenario sections from the question interface, without requiring a return to the main menu, would streamline gameplay and reduce interruptions.

4.4 Logo as a tool to increase acceptance

Logos serve as powerful tools in visual communication, helping convey an organisation or entity's values, mission, and identity. They are integral to brand identity and can influence public perception and emotional responses through their design elements, such as colour and form. Logos often carry deep cultural and social meanings, which can enhance their acceptance and effectiveness. For instance, the design elements of a logo can reflect local sociocultural contexts, making them more relatable and accepted by the target audience (Barbado et al., 2024; Universiti Malaya et al., 2019).

To increase the acceptance of agrifood products fertilised with human excreta, we developed logos for this purpose. To help draw the logos, we used ChatGPT CORA (paid version). In the elaboration, we specified regional characteristics based on the

stakeholder interviews and the surveys. For creating the logos, the following prompt was elaborated and tailored to the pilot case study regions:

“Hi! I need a logo. The logo aims to increase social acceptance of a new innovation. This innovation is a fertiliser and irrigation water (at the same time) processed from reclaimed (waste)water. People are usually afraid of the use of this product and the fruits fertilised with it. In order to increase social acceptance, selling points that can be included in this logo are: By using reclaimed water, you save surface water; It is similar to „free-range eggs” – not organic but more sustainable; It is also part of the „short value chain”, similar to fertilisation with manure. (Fruits are usually avocados and mangos). Emphasise somehow the short value chain.” (The example of the logo prompt for the case study of Spain.)

The following logos were created:

Figure 28: Logos for the Axaquria case

Figure 29: Logos for the German cases

Figure 30: Logos for Gotland case

Feedback

In order to validate the potential usefulness of the logos, we organised a workshop (during the Berlin consortium meeting) with the case study partners. This workshop aimed to improve the potential logos. Not only do the case-specific partners assess their logos, but also partners from other case study regions, in order to get feedback from an “outside observer”. Participants in the workshop were asked to indicate both the positive aspects (what the logos say) and the negative aspects (what is missing).

In the Spain logo, the presence of fruits was assessed as positive, as was the nutrient-rich text in the case of the tomato logo. Participants suggested not to present so many elements on the logo; for instance, a hand is not needed to represent the concept. Some of the participants suggested using circularity instead of reclaimed water.

Figure 31: Results of the workshop in the case of Spanish logos

Based on the workshop's opinions, the following logo can be suggested for use:

Taking into account the opinions of the workshop, the following logo can be suggested for use in the German case:

Figure 34.A suggested new logo for the German case based on the workshop

In the Swedish logos, circular signs, the text “certified,” and the indication of locality were assessed as positive. Participants said there are too many elements in the logo and suggested eliminating the manure. Instead of “urine fertiliser”, “dry fertiliser” text was suggested.

Figure 35: Results of the discussion on the Swedish logos

Based on the suggestions and to include the space specificity of the Swedish case, the following logo is suggested:

Figure 36. A suggested new logo for the Swedish case, based on the workshop

Based on this feedback, the logos can be further processed once the legislation and the certification process allow sufficient use of these products (see Deliverables D3.6 and D3.7⁹).

4.5 Challenges of certifications

4.5.1 The role of certification

A certification can significantly enhance the reputation of a product it represents, and enhance loyalty within targeted communities. This is particularly evident in the adaptive apparel market, where certification signals a commitment to inclusivity and ethical practices (McBee-Black & Sun, 2024). Certification processes can help address stakeholder concerns by ensuring that products and practices meet established standards (Medrano-Berumen & Akbaş, 2020; Sullivan et al., 2025).

Integrating certification early in the planning process can enhance innovation management and reduce market and societal resistance. This approach is particularly relevant in the deployment of emerging technologies, where public engagement and trust are critical (Karytsas & Polyzou, 2021; Lyra, 2025).

Hence, as described in P2Green Deliverable 3.6 and mentioned by our stakeholders (see above) as well, third-party certifications (or similar product assurance systems) can play a role in awareness-raising, and for its marketing/labelling purposes, the above-described logos can be used. The uptake of human excreta-based fertilisers encounters substantial challenges related to social acceptance across all three pilot regions. To mitigate these barriers, the establishment of appropriate certification schemes is identified as a crucial enabling factor. Such schemes would not only ensure the safe use of these fertilisers but also enhance public confidence, thereby stimulating market demand. This view is consistent with De Boer et al. (2018), who emphasise the potential of certification to improve perceptions of the environmental and health safety of eco-fertilisers and, in turn, to strengthen their market position (De Boer et al., 2018)¹⁰.

In the Gotland region, potential certification approaches concern both festival-related and fertiliser-related dimensions. With respect to festivals, it is suggested that a “green certification” could encourage organisers to demand more environmentally friendly sanitation services, thereby increasing interest in nutrient-recycling solutions. In parallel, certification of the fertiliser itself is seen as essential to demonstrate safety and to increase the willingness of farmers and crop buyers to adopt it. Such certification could also function as a communication instrument towards consumers by highlighting the environmental benefits of the products. In this context, a suitable certification option is

⁹ <http://p2green.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/D3.7-Scoping-review-describing-the-status-of-the-legislative-framework.pdf>

¹⁰ P2Green Deliverable 3.6.

currently being explored for Gotland, with the KRAV¹¹ standard identified as a promising avenue, provided that the fertiliser complies with its criteria¹².

For the North German Plain, a comparable fertiliser certification is considered advantageous; however, legal authorisations are required before this can be pursued. Nonetheless, integration with third-party building certification schemes such as BREEAM¹³ may help to generate demand among property owners for the installation of urine treatment technologies¹⁴.

In the Axarquía pilot region, an official certification for end-products grown with reclaimed water is deemed necessary to signal their reduced environmental footprint. At present, most certification schemes do not account for the origin of the water used in production, meaning that the use of reclaimed water remains invisible to end-consumers. Existing labels and standards, therefore, do not fully capture this dimension, indicating a need to develop certification frameworks for products based on circular economy principles in order to enhance the value of the fruit. In this regard, private certification schemes such as GLOBALG.A.P.¹⁵, LEAF Marque¹⁶ or organic labels warrant further investigation¹⁷.

Overall, third-party certification is viewed as a widely used and effective instrument for enhancing social acceptance and credibility among end-consumers in the regions concerned. Certifications that attest to the quality and effectiveness of bio-based fertilisers—whether derived from reclaimed wastewater, urine or faeces—can help to stimulate demand for crops grown with reclaimed water by fostering trust between nutrient-recycling fertiliser producers and farmers. Such mechanisms can verify compliance with health, environmental and agricultural standards, while addressing concerns about contamination, nutrient consistency and public acceptability. In the absence of clear and credible safety assurances, market uptake is likely to remain limited, constraining the potential for these circular solutions to scale¹⁸.

¹¹ The KRAV Standards comply with the EU regulation for organic production, which is a requirement for all production and sales of organic goods within the EU. However, KRAV goes further with stricter standards for animal welfare, environment and health, climate, and better working conditions (KRAV n.d.)

¹² P2GreeN Deliverable 3.6

¹³ Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method (BREEAM) is a certification system used to specify and measure the sustainability performance of buildings, helping to meet sustainability goals over time (BREEAM 2025)

¹⁴ P2GreeN Deliverable 3.6.

¹⁵ GLOBALG.A.P. standards are designed to foster the global adoption of more responsible farming practices. Audits are conducted using methods such as reviewing documentation, conducting interviews, and performing on-site observations. When the criteria are fulfilled, the producer or producer group is awarded certification (GlobalG.A.P. n.d.)

¹⁶ LEAF Marque certification builds on the principles of Integrated Farm Management (IFM) – a whole farm approach utilizing modern technology and traditional methods to deliver prosperous farming enriching the environment and engaging the local communities (LEAF n.d.)

¹⁷ P2GreeN Deliverable 3.6.

¹⁸ P2GreeN Deliverable 3.6.

4.5.2 Feedback – Recognition and acceptance of labelling/certification

As can be seen above, a certificate might be a good tool; however, there are several barriers to its effective use. One of them is its recognition.

Across the EU-27, product quality (97%) and price (94%) are the dominant drivers of purchasing decisions, while around three-quarters of respondents (73%) say that environmental impact is also an important criterion. Most Europeans agree that buying products with a lower environmental impact makes a difference (81% total agree), and a majority report having already chosen products for this reason. However, awareness of the EU Ecolabel logo itself remains limited: only 38% of EU citizens recognise it, and France is the only country where a majority (61%) report having seen the logo. Nonetheless, among those who know it, knowledge of its core features is relatively good: majorities correctly understand that products must meet strict environmental criteria and have a lower impact than alternatives, and roughly three-quarters of Europeans say they trust that EU Ecolabel products really are more environmentally friendly¹⁹.

In terms of cross-country patterns, Italy, Spain, Greece and France all show relatively strong pro-environmental orientations and comparatively high interest in finding more EU Ecolabel products across categories such as textiles, cosmetics, paints and absorbent hygiene products. Italy stands out for frequent purchasing of products with environmental labels and has one of the highest reported frequencies of buying EU Ecolabel products specifically. Spain and Greece combine great concern about environmental impact with strong demand for more labelled products, especially in categories like tourist accommodation and hygiene products. France is distinctive for its very high logo recognition and above-average self-reported purchasing of EU Ecolabel products. Sweden and Germany show solid but more moderate engagement: environmental impact is important, trust in the EU Ecolabel is high, but awareness of the logo is only around one third and self-reported purchasing is closer to the EU average. Hungary broadly shares the EU-level belief that environmental impact matters and shows reasonably good knowledge of the label's meaning, but it combines relatively low awareness of the logo (around one-fifth) with comparatively low frequency of buying environmentally labelled and EU Ecolabel products, and only mid-range demand for expanding the offer of EU Ecolabel goods²⁰.

¹⁹ <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/3072>

²⁰ <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/3072>

4.5.3 Feedback – Certification challenges in legislation

As we described in Deliverable 3.7, certification has a legal barrier as well.

First, the D3.7 report highlights the role of the Fertilising Products Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 (FPR) as the core EU “certification” framework for fertilisers. Products that meet the FPR’s technical, safety and labelling requirements can be placed on the market as EU fertilising products and carry the CE mark, which signals conformity with harmonised Union legislation and enables free circulation across the EU/EEA.

Compliance is demonstrated through a conformity assessment that checks (i) whether the product fits into one of the defined Product Function Categories (PFCs) and (ii) whether its ingredients are covered by the relevant Component Material Categories (CMCs), combined with appropriate labelling and documentation. Non-CE products must rely on national authorisation and bilateral mutual recognition procedures, which can be more costly and uncertain²¹.

Second, certification for organic production is governed primarily by Regulation (EU) 2018/848 and its Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/1165. These lay down principles, control and certification procedures for organic production, and explicitly link the right to use organic labels and claims to compliance with detailed rules and official controls. For fertilisers and soil improvers, only products whose ingredients are listed in Annex II of Regulation (EU) 2021/1165 and which meet the specific conditions set there can be certified as suitable for use in organic farming. This list is often more restrictive than general market rules. In addition to the public system, the report notes the existence of private certification schemes (e.g. Ecocert, CAAE), which certify inputs (such as fertilising products) as “allowed in organic farming” under EU rules; national authorities must still validate suitability, and approved products may be listed in official registries and labelled accordingly²².

Against this background, the D3.7 report stresses that P2Green’s urine- and faeces-based fertilising products currently face structural certification gaps. Under the FPR, there is at present no clearly suitable CMC for human urine or faecal matter, which prevents these products from qualifying as EU fertilising products with CE marking. Only the compost-based KIT product might potentially fit into a CMC, and even that requires further legal clarification. Further to this, examination of a number of other requirements defined in the Regulation must also be performed so that it can be deemed compliant with FPR. Similarly, because human excreta are not listed among the authorised materials for use in organic farming, these products cannot yet be certified as suitable for use in organic production. It means that in the medium term, policy change may be needed—such as creating a new CMC for treated human excreta or amending existing categories—while in the short term P2Green products must rely on national

²¹ P2Green Deliverable 3.7.

²² P2Green Deliverable 3.7.

authorisation regimes and mutual recognition rather than EU-wide certification pathways, and can only be used in conventional farming²³.

4.6 The use of a practical example

The example of the workshop organised by a Paris stakeholder shows a good example of the role of the tool as a practical example (also analysed in Chapter 3.2.7). During the workshops [organised with the panel of future residents to raise awareness], the workshop organiser brought along biscuits fertilised with urine (Figure 37). Packets of biscuits were handed out. At the start of the workshop, people didn't touch the packets. Then, after the workshop and the explanations, people tasted the biscuits and left with packets.

Figure 37. Biscuits. Some of its ingredients were cultivated on a field where human-based fertiliser was used.

Source: <https://www.leesu.fr/ocapi/2023/12/01/les-biscodors-2023-sont-en-sachet/>

²³ P2GreenN Deliverable 3.7.

5 Overall conclusions

This deliverable set out to investigate the social acceptance of human excreta-derived fertilisers (HEDF) across seven European regions, using three complementary empirical approaches: an online survey among lay citizens, focus group discussions with key stakeholders, and semi-structured expert interviews. In addition, a toolbox of communication and engagement instruments was developed to address the barriers and opportunities identified. Taken together, these components provide a multi-layered picture of how acceptance of HEDF is shaped by risk perceptions, institutional trust, NIMBY attitudes, willingness to pay and local contextual factors, and how these can be addressed in practice.

Across methods and countries, several robust patterns emerge. First, the survey and the qualitative material converge in showing that farmers are generally more open to HEDF than consumers, provided that agronomic performance is reliable, prices are competitive, and products are appropriately licensed. This resonates with the survey findings on willingness to pay (WTP): while stated WTP for vegetables fertilised with human-derived products decreases from North to South and East, the focus groups and interviews consistently describe farmers as pragmatically weighing cost and yield, whereas consumers react more strongly to symbolic aspects such as labels, terminology (“wastewater”, “human excreta”) and organic certification. Second, all three methods underline that odour and contamination (including pharmaceutical and hormone residues) are the dominant concerns, with infection seen as less salient. This pattern is clearly visible in the survey ratings of specific risks. It is echoed in stakeholder narratives, where odour, water quality, and residues feature prominently in Spain, Greece, Hungary, and Italy. At the same time, Sweden and Germany appear more relaxed but still cautious.

The triangulation also highlights a shared structure of institutional trust and NIMBY attitudes. Survey results show that respondents in all countries place more trust in private companies than in governments when it comes to building and operating safe facilities. However, absolute levels and gaps vary by context. The qualitative material adds nuance by specifying which actors are expected to play leading roles: local governments and municipalities, water utilities, and, in some cases, private companies and NGOs are repeatedly identified as the most credible communicators and facilitators. The NIMBY pattern is similarly consistent: survey respondents in every country are more accepting of nearby green areas fertilised with HEDF than of a processing facility near their home, with Sweden and Germany showing the highest acceptance and Hungary and Greece the lowest. The focus groups and interviews confirm strong NIMBY dynamics in the latter cases, linked to fears about odour, traffic, landscape impacts, and coastal pollution, while also pointing to the importance of transparent procedures, prior experience with environmental investments, and visible local benefits in mitigating opposition.

At the same time, comparing methods for the same topics reveals important differences and refinements. In Hungary, for example, the survey indicates relatively high trust in private actors alongside low trust in government, whereas interviews stress that companies are not fully trusted on their own; rather, joint communication by municipalities, civil society and “correct” politicians is seen as essential. In Italy and Greece, the survey’s lower WTP and greater concerns are complemented by qualitative evidence of a strong expectation of participation and co-design: residents are more willing to accept facilities and products when they feel treated as co-owners rather than passive recipients. In Sweden and Germany, the relatively favourable survey scores on NIMBY and WTP are mirrored by stakeholders’ accounts of high generalised trust and prior familiarity with similar practices (e.g. urine use, farmyard manure), but the interviews also point to strategic choices around transparency.

The toolbox of engagement instruments is directly informed by, and responds to, these cross-method insights. Both physical and online field visits are designed to make abstract environmental challenges (such as water scarcity) and circular solutions tangibly visible, thereby addressing the gap between pro-environmental attitudes and concrete behavioural support identified in the survey and interviews. The video game “Turning Waste into Green Wealth” and the logo exercises explicitly tackle terminology, framing and risk communication, exploring how different visual and narrative choices can normalise HEDF by focusing on circularity, local resource use and environmental benefits rather than on “waste”. Certification emerges as a particularly important bridging mechanism: both the empirical work and the legislative review emphasise that third-party certification can simultaneously provide safety assurances to farmers and consumers, differentiate products in the market and serve as a trusted communication tool. Finally, the practical example of wine produced with reclaimed water illustrates how high-quality, tangible products can symbolically anchor the idea that circular solutions are not only safe but desirable.

Overall, the combined evidence suggests that the social acceptance of HEDF is neither uniformly low nor automatically guaranteed; it is conditional, context-dependent and strongly mediated by trust, framing and institutional arrangements. Surveys capture broad spatial gradients in trust, NIMBY attitudes, perceived risks and WTP, while focus groups and interviews reveal the narratives, actors and local histories underpinning these patterns. Together, they indicate that successful deployment of HEDF will require:

- targeting farmers and environmentally conscious consumer niches as early adopters;
- carefully choosing language and labels that emphasise circularity, local resource use and environmental co-benefits rather than “waste”;
- building multi-actor coalitions in which local authorities, utilities, companies and experts communicate jointly and transparently;

- using experimental and visual tools (field visits, games, logos, product examples) to make the benefits and safeguards tangible;
- developing robust, context-appropriate certification schemes that integrate health, environmental and circular economy criteria.

If these conditions are met and adapted to local socio-political contexts, HEDF can move from niche experiments towards broader societal acceptance and play a meaningful role in closing nutrient loops in line with the EU Green Deal and Farm to Fork objectives.

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7 Annex

7.1 The online survey

Social acceptance – Survey

Linked to the EU's Green Deal and the idea of a Circular Economy, the main aim of the [P2Green project](#) is to support innovations that turn human sanitary waste into fertiliser.

At the same time, we believe that innovation and the circular economy can only be effective if we take into account society's attitude and acceptance of innovation. The questionnaire seeks to answer this.

Within the survey, you will be asked for some personal data. Responses will be anonymised.

Should you have any questions about this Call for Evidence, or the SSH CENTRE project more broadly, please contact Viktor Varjú (varju.viktor@krtk.hu, survey supervisor).

Starting the survey, I understand and accept that a minimum of personal data (gender, age, occupation, social status) are recorded by the host server at the premises of the P2Green partner and protected by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). They cannot be used for purposes other than the one for which they were gathered (understanding social acceptance). They are for the exclusive use of their recipient (KRTK) and are subject to confidentiality. (Data protection guidelines can be found here: <https://adatbank.krtk.mta.hu/en/adatvedelem/>)

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1. Please indicate the year of your birth:

2. Please, indicate your gender:

- Woman
- Man
- Non-binary
- Prefer to self-describe:.....
- Prefer not to say

3. What is your nationality?

....

4. In which country do you currently live?

...

5. What is your highest level of education? (Choose one.)

- a. primary school
- b. secondary school
- c. Bachelor's degree
- d. Masters' degree
- e. PhD/DLA
- f. Other, please specify:.....
- h. No answer

6. How would you describe your profession? (Choose one.)

- a. student
- b. employed
- c. self-employed
- d. unemployed
- e. retired
- f. apprentice
- g. Other, please specify...
- h. No answer

7. What kind of work do you do?

1. intellectual, degree required
2. intellectual, non-degree required
3. physical, skilled
4. manual, skilled worker
5. manual, unskilled worker
6. farmer
7. self-employed trader, service provider
8. self-employed producer, non-agricultural
9. Other, please specify:...

8. Which of the following best describes the financial situation of your household?

1. we live without financial problems and we can save substantial money
2. we can manage our monthly income well and we can save some money as well
3. our income just covers our expenses
4. we have financial problems from month to month
5. we live in poverty
0. does not wish to answer

9. On a scale of 1 to 10, please rate how threatening you think the following social problems are (1 = not threatening at all, 10 = very threatening. You can also use a value in between)

- | | | |
|-----------------------------|----------------------|----------|
| 1. Healthcare | 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 | 0(KN/NA) |
| 2. Armed conflicts | 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 | 0(KN/NA) |
| 3. Pandemics | 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 | 0(KN/NA) |
| 4. Inflation | 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 | 0(KN/NA) |
| 5. climate change | 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 | 0(KN/NA) |
| 6. migration | 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 | 0(KN/NA) |
| 7. unemployment | 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 | 0(KN/NA) |
| 8. education | 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 | 0(KN/NA) |
| 9. poverty, hunger | 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 | 0(KN/NA) |
| 10. terrorism | 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 | 0(KN/NA) |
| 11. overpopulation | 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 | 0(KN/NA) |
| 12. water scarcity | 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 | 0(KN/NA) |
| 13. environmental pollution | 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 | 0(KN/NA) |

10. How much do you agree with the following. Please rate the statements from 1 to 10, where 1=strongly disagree and 10=strongly agree. You can also use a value in between.

- 10.a) I often read about the latest technologies
1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)
- 10.b) I usually use the latest technologies (e.g. in mobile phone; machines) in my
life
1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)
- 10.c) I trust that companies in the private sector ensure that safe facilities are built.
1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)
- 10.d) I trust that companies in the private sector operate this system safely.
1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)
- 10.e) I trust that the government or the responsible state authorities adequately
consider the needs of local residents.
1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)
- 10.f) I trust that the government or the responsible state authorities make a
responsible decision whether a new technology can be introduced or not.
1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)
- 10.g) I trust that the government or the responsible state authorities will carry out
safety checks to ensure safe operation.
1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)
10. h) The environment is important to me.
1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)
- 10.e) My lifestyle is perceived by my friends as environmentally aware.
1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)

11. Imagine that a facility that creates fertilizers from human urine/excrement or waste water would be built next to your place of residence. What kind of feelings does that evoke in you? 1-10 scale; 1 = very negative feelings disagree, 10 = very positive feelings

1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)

12. Imagine, that the field/park/green area next to your place of residence is fertilised by a fertiliser transformed from human urine/excrement or reclaimed water from waste water. What kind of feelings does that evoke in you? 1-10 scale; 1 = very negative feelings disagree, 10 = very positive feelings

1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)

12.a: What do you feel exactly?

...

12.b: How much do you worry about the followings? (Please rate your worry from 1 to 10, where 1=you are not worried about it at all; and 10= you are very much worried. You can also use a value in between.)

Worry about the stink/smell 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)

Worry about the infection 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)

Worry about the environmental contamination of the soil/water 1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-10 0(KN/NA)

13. Imagine that you can buy three types of vegetables in a market. One is fertilized by a.) artificial fertiliser, one is fertilised with b.) fertiliser made from animal manure, and the third is fertilized with c.) fertiliser made from human urine/waste water. Which would you choose:

13.a) If all three vegetables have the same price. The one fertilised by:

- a.) artificial fertiliser,
 - b.) fertiliser made from animal manure
 - c.) fertiliser made from human urine/waste water
- 0- KN/NA

13.b) If the cheapest vegetable is the one that was fertilised by fertiliser made from human urine/waste water:

- a.) artificial fertiliser,
 - b.) fertiliser made from animal manure
 - c.) fertiliser made from human urine/waste water
- 0- KN/NA

13.c) If all three vegetables have the same price and the one that was fertilised by fertiliser made from human urine/waste water seems to be the healthiest:

- a.) artificial fertiliser,

- b.) fertiliser made from animal manure
- c.) fertiliser made from human urine/waste water
- 0- KN/NA

13.d) Imagine, that there are two types of vegetables on the market. One is fertilised with cheap artificial fertiliser, the other (more expensive) with fertiliser made from human urine/waste water. The latter, however, is 100% environmentally friendly, sustainable and follows the principles of a circular economy. How much more would you be willing to pay for this vegetable? (Please choose one.)

- a) I do not want to pay more
- b) I can pay 50% more
- c) I would pay double for it
- d) I would pay triple for it
- e) I do not know

14. In case you would like to receive information about the results of this survey, please write here to your e-mail address:

7.2 Focus group questions

Focus group guidance

The focus group should contain 6-8 people. In case there are more stakeholders are participating in the workshop, the organiser should choose 6 to 8. Preferably, the 6-8 people should be different types of stakeholders.

The interview should be recorded, therefore a GDPR/consent? form is needed.

Parallel with recording, during the interview, the interviewer should take notes. Notes should not be long sentences but short comments. But what is also important is that the interviewer writes what idea is coming from whom. (No need for name just type of stakeholder.)

Below, you can see the main guiding questions. However, we also would like to leave the possibility to the interviewer to react on the spot and ask relating questions if she/he sees as it useful. It is also suggested to ask the respondents to clarify the answer if there is any doubt that the answers are not clearly understandable.

As this is a “remote” focus group interview, it would be nice to ask the respondents to reply in longer sentences keeping in mind that the interviewer (remote interviewer) do not know the circumstances/local culture properly.

The interviewer must always try to get the other participants to speak as well. Especially when you have an opinion leader.

Guiding questions

How innovative do you find the solution discussed at the workshop?

Do you have any objections to the novelty discussed here? If so, what?

Would you use this new kind of toilets in your home? if so, why? If not, why?

How would you feel if you knew that a product you can buy in a store (e.g., vegetables) is not fertilized in the traditional way, but with nutrients made from urine?

Would you buy such products? If so, why? If not, why?

Now, please think about people in your community and imagine how they are thinking.

How open do you think the people living here are to new things and innovations in general?

What do you think people in your environment/community would like to use such a special toilette in their home? If so, why? If not, why?

How do you think people in your community would react if they knew that the surrounding farms were using manure made from human urine instead of artificial fertilizers?

Do you think people in your community would buy vegetables that they know are grown with manure made from human urine instead of artificial fertilizers?

And if you were to sell the vegetables, would people prefer to buy such products from you?

7.3 Semi-structured interview questions

Interview questions

Linked to the EU's Green Deal and the idea of a Circular Economy, the main aim of the [P2GreenN](#) project is to support innovations that turn human sanitary waste into fertiliser.

At the same time, we believe that innovation and the circular economy can only be effective if we take into account society's attitude and acceptance of innovation. The interview seeks to answer this via the opinion and experience of key stakeholders who can contribute to the introduction of this kind of innovation.

The length of the interview is no more than 30 minutes.

Responding to the questions you agree and declare that you have read the information on [data management](#) of the interview organiser (KRTK GDPR) and You give your consent to the Data Controller to process your personal data for documentation purposes only. Your responses will be used confidentially and anonymised.

If you wish to read the final report of this research, please send us your e-mail address.

In case you enquire any questions, please contact viktor.varju@krtk.hun-ren.hu

Basic questions, filled by the interviewer

Gender of the respondent:

Age of the respondent:

Sector, the interviewee working in:

Pilot/follower region:

Which are the most important challenges humankind has to face in the coming years/decades?

How is this challenge affect your life?

When you hear the word “innovation”, what is your first thought about this notion?

Describe a situation in which you embraced a new system, process, technology, or idea at work that was a major departure from the old way of doing things. What were the reactions in general?

Imagine, that as an innovation, a treatment facility/object is planned to be built in your neighbourhood. What are the aspects do you think local citizens are afraid of the most? (e.g., odour, noise, visual pollution, other?) Please, explain, why?

When a new treatment facility/object is planned to be built, who has to communicate this plan to the citizens do you think? (e.g. Is it the investor private company, or the local government, or the local NGO?) Who can tell them that this is good? Please explain why. (In whom do the citizens trust the most?)

How strong the **local government** in your region is do you think? How strong is the local governments' lobbying capacity for new investments?

How strong the **local NGOs** in your region is do you think? How strong is the NGOs' lobbying capacity for new investments?

Usually, is there a public hearing for citizens before any investment in your region? If so, in your knowledge, how does this public process usually take place?

Which are the most important information outlets the local citizens in your region trust the most (even if they are regular or social media platforms, neighbourhood talks, opinions of the next-door neighbour, or opinions of relatives)? Please explain your response.

Do you see any generational or gender differences? If so, how does this appear?

If this investment is an investment that creates fertiliser from human extracts, does it make any change relating to the above-mentioned?

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Deliverable 3.4

Do you see any negative impact of such an investment? (E.g. On environment, on tourism, on local society etc.?)

Do you think that such an investment can generate jobs or economic benefits for the locals? How do you see, locals applying for vacancies/jobs in a such firm?

If there is a possibility for community finance, do you think that locals can invest in such an investment? If so, Why? If not, why?

Is there anything you would like to add?

7.4 Questionnaire of the field visit

P2GreeN survey on field visits

Dear Colleagues,

In this short survey, we would like to ask you to evaluate the field visits of the P2GreeN project. This is for internal use for T3.3. delivery/report and toolbox in order to point out what are the challenges and potential of field visits are to get more acceptance of new innovative solutions (like the ones in P2G).

The survey is anonymous, and the responses will be aggregated for the analysis. Regardless you took part or not in any of the field visits in the pilots, please fill it in. Thank you for your help!

By clicking the next button, you understand that your contribution is entirely voluntary and the aggregated results can be used for research purposes under the P2GreeN project. You are free to omit any questions. You understand that participants have a right to access the outcomes of conducted research, and no personal data will be recorded.

1. How much do you agree with the following definition?
(Please rate it in a 1 to 10 Likert scale, where 1 means “I do not agree at all” while 10 means “I fully agree”. You can choose you can also choose the integers between 1 and 10 to refine your response.)

Field visit is a learning experience where individuals directly observe and interact with real-world settings to gain firsthand knowledge and understanding of a subject or situation.

2. Is there anything else you think is important in a field visit?

3. How important do you think a field visit is to dispel any doubts?
(Please rate it in a 1 to 10 Likert scale, where 1 means “It is not important at all” while 10 means “It is very important”. You can choose you can also choose the integers between 1 and 10 to refine your response.)

4. In which of the following field visit you are attended (partly or entirely)?

[Itt legyen lehetőség mindhárom opció kiválasztására, illetve ha a non-of-them-et választja, akkor csak azt választhassa.]

- a.) Field visit(s) in Malaga (Axarquía region)
- b.) Field visit(s) in Gotland
- c.) Field visit(s) in Brandenburg-Hamburg regions/German pilots (accompanied by the Berlin COM)
- d.) non of them

These questions are posed as many times as the respondents participated in the field visits of the pilot regions in “Axarquía region (Malaga)”; “Gotland”; “German pilots”.

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5. How much do you think the “CASE STUDY REGION NAME” field visits help to better understand what is going on in the pilot?

(1-10 Likert scale: 1 – It did not help at all; 10- it helped very much)

6. What was the most important aspect for you?

7. What did you miss during the field visit?

8. How much do you think the field visit could help sceptics to reduce their doubts towards the application of new fertiliser solutions, in connection with the following “acceptance aspects”? (1-10 Likert scale: 1 – It did not reduce doubts at all; 10 – It reduced the doubts totally) [Legyen még az 1-10 mellett egy olyan 0-ás opció, hogy “I do not think this is a doubt”

- a.) In case of smell: 0-10
- b.) In case of noise: 0-10
- c.) In case of visual pollution: 0-10
- d.) In case of sanitation/hygiene: 0-10
- e.) In case of the potential to replace traditional fertilisers: 0-10
- g.) In case to convince local decision makers: 0-10
- h.) In case to convince regional decision makers: 0-10
- i.) In case to convince national decision makers: 0-10
- j.) In case to reduce the assessment of waste water/urine as a negative (criminalised) issue: 0-10
- k.) in case to save water: 0-10
- l1.) [Specific response in the case of Spanish region] In case to use reclaimed water based fertiliser for agrifood production
- l2.) [Specific response in the case of Gotland] In case to use urine based fertiliser for agrifood production
- l3.) [Specific response in the case of German region] In case to use urine/fecal based fertiliser for agrifood production.
- m.) anything else?

Thank you for your response

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